

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF MACHINE LEARNING MODELS FOR PIXEL-WISE ACID MINE DRAINAGE CLASSIFICATION USING SENTINEL-2

Fahimeh Farahnakian, Johanna Torppa, Nike Luodes, Hannu Panttila, Teemu Karlsson

Geological Survey of Finland (GTK), Finland

ABSTRACT

Acid Mine Drainage (AMD) is a type of water pollution that occurs when sulfur-bearing minerals in rocks and soil are exposed to air and water. This paper explores the application of Machine Learning (ML) algorithms for pixel-level classification of AMD from Sentinel-2 imagery. The proposed algorithms include Random Forest (RF), K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN), Logistic Regression (LR), and Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP). They classify each pixel in the imagery as AMD or non-AMD. To generate more training samples and improve the performance of ML methods, we use a window-based approach and the SMOTE technique [1]. Best hyper-parameter of ML methods are selected based on the greedy forward selection approach. The study also investigates the relative importance of different spectral bands of Sentinel-2 for AMD classification. The experimental results are collected on three lakes in Outokumpu mining region, Finland. The results demonstrate that RF model exhibits the best classification performance with accuracy of 97.74%.

Index Terms— AMD mapping, machine learning, remote sensing, multispectral imagery

1. INTRODUCTION

AMD is a serious environmental problem that arises from the oxidation of sulfide-rich rocks in abandoned mines or mining-disturbed areas. It can contaminate water sources and harm ecosystems. Therefore, monitoring AMD is important to identify and prioritize areas where AMD is a problem and control AMD. Some related works [2–6] show that remote sensing techniques such as Sentinel-2 satellite data have emerged as an effective tool for monitoring and predicting AMD occurrence. Sentinel-2 has a spatial resolution of up to 10 meters, enabling the identification of fine-scale land cover features and environmental changes. In addition, it acquires data globally every five days, providing a synoptic view of AMD affected areas and the ability to monitor changes over time.

Over the past decade, ML methods have emerged the powerful tool for AMD mapping [2, 3]. However, these su-

This work is part of the Secure and Sustainable Supply of raw materials for EU Industry (S34I) project funded by European Union.

Fig. 1: The location map of study area, Outokumpu, Finland.

pervised ML algorithms require a labelled dataset for learning the patterns or relationships between the input variables and the target variable. Creating labelled data is usually expensive, resource-intensive and time-consuming in numerous real-world applications specifically in this field. For this reason, to apply ML methods, we usually face with imbalanced data problem as there are a few samples with known class and many samples of unknown class. In our case study, we have 10 water samples as ground truth from three AMD-affected lakes. The well-known ML methods (RF, LR, KNN and MLP) are evaluated on three AMD lakes in Outokumpu region which are acidic runoff originating from active or abandoned mining sites. They classify each pixel of a Sentinel-2 imagery into "AMD" or "non-AMD" class. We employed SMOTE (Synthetic Minority Oversampling) technique [1] to address the imbalanced data problem by adding new samples from the minority class (AMD). In addition, we proposed a window-based approach and determined a specific area around each water sample which is affected by AMD in order to produce more samples for the AMD class. For non-AMD class, we collected samples from a nearby lake with similar geological characteristics to the AMD-affected lakes. The best hyper-parameters of ML models are selected based on the Greedy Forward Selection (GFS) method. The results show that RF outperforms than other ML methods. We also investigate the importance of each band of Sentinel-2 imagery for AMD mapping by training ML models based on each band individually. From the results, we found green and blue bands are the most important bands for distinguishing between AMD and non-AMD classes. We believe that our findings have important implications for the development of

more accurate and efficient ML-based methods for pixel-wise AMD classification.

2. STUDY AREA

The study area, Outokumpu, is an AMD-affected site which is located in the North Karelia region in eastern Finland (Fig. 1). Three multi-metal (Cobalt, Nickel, Zinc) also Gold, Silver and pyrite concentrate underground mines in Outokumpu region. The mining activities had significant environmental impacts and large areas outside the mines were affected by mine waste and low-quality drainage, especially the lakes Outolampi, Alimmainen Hautalampi and Sysmäjärvi. Currently, some environmental impacts have been addressed, but e.g., Outolampi, which is located in the tailing's area of the old mine, remains severely polluted.

3. DATA

3.1. Sentinel-2 Satellite Multispectral Imagery

In this study, we downloaded Sentinel-2 data from FinHub¹ service from May to November 2023 for the quantitative assessment of AMD in three study lakes. Sentinel-2 For AMD-related tasks, the preferred choice is usually Sentinel-2 Level-2A data because of its atmospheric correction and suitability for water quality assessment [3, 5, 6]. Moreover, L2A data allows for the more accurate detection of changes in water bodies and the identification of AMD-affected areas. Fig. 2 shows an example Sentinel-2 image over the Outokumpu region with three AMD lakes and a non-AMD lake on the top. We use seven bands out of Sentinel-2 which are typically useful for AMD mapping and have maximum resolution 10 m and 20 m. They are included: B2 (490 nm), B3 (560 nm), B4 (665 nm), B8 (842 nm), B8A (865 nm), B11 (1610 nm) and B12 (2190 nm). All the bands of Sentinel-2 image were resampled to 10 m and the interest lakes are clipped from the images. Images with cloud cover and sun glint over the water bodies were discarded.

3.2. Water sampling

Water sampling can be considered a ground truth for AMD prediction, as it directly measures the water quality and can confirm the presence of AMD. We measure the critical data on parameters such as pH levels, metal concentrations (e.g., iron, aluminum, manganese), sulfate concentrations, and other chemical characteristics associated with AMD. These measurements are essential for assessing the potential environmental impact of AMD and for making informed decisions regarding mitigation and remediation efforts. The sampling at the Outolampi, Hautalampi and Sysmäjärvi lakes was conducted during 29-30 of August 2023. A total of 10 surface

Fig. 2: True-color image of an example of Sentinel-2 in June 10th, 2023 over the Outokumpu region for three AMD lakes (Outolampi, Alimmainen Hautalampi and Sysmäjärvi) and one non-AMD lake (Kussjärvi).

water samples were collected for analysis (see Fig. 3). Two samples were obtained from each of the lakes Outolampi and Alimmainen Hautalampi, representing a subset of the sampling locations. The larger lake, Sysmäjärvi, was sampled six times to provide a more comprehensive assessment of its water quality. More details about the value of pH level and Fe and SO₄ concentrations are demonstrated on Fig. 3. The sampling was conducted utilizing a small rubber boat. The sampling weather was cloudy, with the showers of rain and air temperature of around 16 °C.

4. METHODS

We evaluated the effectiveness of four well-known ML techniques for AMD pixel-level classification including Random Forest (RF), K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN), Logistic Regression (LR), and Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP). RF [7] is an ensemble learning method known for its robustness and accuracy in various applications. RF can handle large datasets with high dimensionality, while providing estimates of feature importance. RF utilizes numerous decision trees during the training phase, each of which is independently developed, with the final output being determined by aggregating their individual predictions. KNN [8] is a versatile, non-parametric algorithm used for classification and regression. It operates by identifying the K nearest data points to a query point and making predictions based on the majority vote (classification) or average (regression) of these neighbours. LR model [9] arises from the goal of modeling posterior probabilities of discrete K classes with linear functions of explanatory variables, while ensuring that the posterior probabilities sum to one and remain in the interval $[0, 1]$. (MLP) [10] is a simple feedforward neural network that is composed of multiple layers of perceptrons. MLP typically consists of at least three layers of nodes: an input layer, a hidden layer and an output layer. In the prediction task, the purpose of MLP neural network is typically to train the neural network to minimize the difference between output and objective by adjusting the weights of the inputs within the layers.

The best hyper-parameters of the proposed ML models are selected by GFS. The main advantage of this algorithm

¹<https://finhub.nasdc.fmi.fi/##/home>

Fig. 3: The sampling locations for the surface water samples for three study AMD lakes.

Fig. 4: The classification accuracy of KNN, RF, LR and MLP for three lakes.

is its simplicity and generally low run-time. It starts with an empty set of parameters and at each step, it adds the parameter that improves the performance of the model the most. The best value of the main parameters of each model is listed at Table 1. The parameter names at the table align with the standard parameter names used in the Scikit-learn Python package.

To improve the performance of ML methods and address imbalanced data, we employed two techniques. (1) SMOTE that randomly pick a point from the minority class and compute the k-nearest neighbors for this point. The synthetic points are added between the chosen point and its neighbors. (2) We also used 10-fold Stratified Cross Validation (SCV) [11] technique to divide the dataset into training and validation datasets during training. SCV as one of the standard methods in order to evaluate the generalization accuracy of a classifier. Compared with the standard CV, SCV ensures that each fold of a dataset has the same distribution of classes.

5. RESULTS

We evaluated four ML models for pixel-wise AMD classification. To generate more samples of AMD class, we assumed a window approach which determine a window $n \times n$ around each water sample where it is allocated in the center of the window. For two Outolampi and Hautalampi, n is 5 that roughly an area of 50 m in diameter is covered. For bigger lake, Sysmäjärvi, n is 10. The window size is corresponds

Fig. 5: The classification results of the baseline ML methods based on the number of bands (features).

to the area of around each water sample where is contaminated with AMD. For non-AMD class, we extract the samples from a clean lake (Kuusjärvi) near to the test lakes. The total samples for AMD and non-AMD classes are 19,761 and 10,337 respectively. Fig. 4 shows the total accuracy of ML methods for three lakes. It demonstrates the maximum accuracy is obtained from RF. The results also indicate that the model achieves a higher performance of 97.74% for the larger lake (Sysmäjärvi) due to the increased availability of training data. Fig. 5 shows the evolution of the classification accuracy for each model based on the number of selected bands. The x-axis shows the number of bands which are included to perform classification. The result shows that we can improve the performance of ML methods by adding more information from different bands.

Table 1: The best value of main hyper-parameters of each model which are selected by GFS.

Model	Hyper_parameter	Value
KNN	n_neighbors	5
	n_estimators	10
RF	max_depth	100
	regularization_coefs	0.25
LR	penalty	L2
	hidden_layer_size	[10 10]

We also investigate the importance of each band for AMD prediction by the proposed ML models. Fig. 6 shows the feature importance scores for seven bands out of Sentinel-2 for our baseline models. From the result, we found the bands B3, B8 and B4 have the highest importance score for our mod-

Fig. 6: The feature importance scores for seven bands of Sentinel-2 image for each baseline method.

els. The reason is they provide more information about various surface features, including water bodies, vegetation health and soil. The green band (B3), with a central wavelength of 560 nm is more sensitive to the absorption of chlorophyll than other bands. This means that it can better detect changes in vegetation health, which can be an early indicator of AMD. To further illustrate the ability of the best model (RF) to effectively acquire AMD semantic information, we visualized the classification maps for each study lake. Fig. 7 shows the prediction maps for three lakes. The visualization indicated that the RF model accurately classified the pixels, as the lakes were primarily contaminated by AMD rather than near-shore areas.

6. CONCLUSION

In this study, we employed Sentinel-2 data and four popular machine learning algorithms to generate AMD classification map. The map classifies each pixel to AMD or non-AMD class. To address imbalance data problem in our case study, we use SMOTE (Synthetic Minority Oversampling) technique. We also used the grid search to find the best hyperparameter for each ML method. The experimental results are collected on three lakes in Outokumpu mining site which are affected by mine waste and low-quality drainage. The results show that we can get high classification accuracy from RF compared with other three employed ML methods. We also

Fig. 7: Prediction map of the best model (RF) for three study lakes and their water samples.

investigated the feature (band) importance of Sentinel-2 for AMD mapping. The findings of the study demonstrate that innovative machine learning algorithms and Sentinel-2 can effectively distinguish between AMD-prone and non-AMD areas, providing a valuable tool for regional-scale AMD mapping. As future works, we plan to perform AMD mapping as a time series analysis which is dealing with temporal data and want to predict AMD trends over time. We intend to explore more opportunities for fusing data from different resources such as EndMap, Worldview3 and drone-based UAV imagery. Moreover, we have plan to evaluate the impact of the most important spectral water indices on the model performance.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] Kevin W. Bowyer, Nitesh V. Chawla, Lawrence O. Hall, and W. Philip Kegelmeyer, “SMOTE: synthetic minority over-sampling technique,” *CoRR*, vol. abs/1106.1813, 2011.
- [2] Melisa Isgró, M. Basallote, Isabel Caballero, and Luis Barbero, “Comparison of uas and sentinel-2 multispectral imagery for water quality monitoring: A case study for acid mine drainage affected areas (sw spain),” *Remote Sensing*, vol. 14, pp. 4053, 08 2022.
- [3] Delira Hanelli, Andreas Barth, Gerald Volkmer, and Martin Köhler, “Modelling of acid mine drainage in open pit lakes using sentinel-2 time-series: A case study from lusatia, germany,” vol. 13, 02 2023.
- [4] Veronika Kopačková, “Mapping acid mine drainage (amd) and acid sulfate soils using sentinel-2 data,” in *IGARSS 2019 - 2019 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium*, 2019, pp. 5682–5685.
- [5] Muhammad Rendana, Wan Idris, and Sahibin Abd Rahim, “Mapping chini lake (pahang, malaysia) using sentinel-2 images to determine the effect of acid mine drainage in the pre- to post-covid-19 restriction period,” *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, vol. 195, 12 2022.
- [6] Aliyeh Seifi, Mahdiah Hosseinjanizadeh, Hojjatolah Ranjbar, and Mehdi Honarmand, “Identification of acid mine drainage potential using sentinel 2a imagery and field data,” *Mine Water and the Environment*, vol. 38, pp. 707 – 717, 2019.
- [7] Leo Breiman, “Random forests,” *Mach. Learn.*, vol. 45, no. 1, pp. 5–32, oct 2001.
- [8] T. Cover and P. Hart, “Nearest neighbor pattern classification,” *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 21–27, 1967.
- [9] Trevor Hastie, Robert Tibshirani, and Jerome Friedman, *The elements of statistical learning: data mining, inference and prediction*, Springer, 2 edition, 2009.
- [10] C.M. Bishop, *Neural networks for pattern recognition*, Oxford University Press, USA, 1995.
- [11] Xinchuan Zeng and Tony R. Martinez, “Distribution-balanced stratified cross-validation for accuracy estimation,” *Journal of Experimental & Theoretical Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 1–12, 2000.